

p-TSA Catalysed One Pot Green Synthesis of Spiro Indole Thiazolidinones

Suraj Singh

Research scholar, Department of Pharmacy, Sunrise University, Alwar (Raj.)

Dr. Kuldeep Singh Patel

Research Supervisor, Department of Pharmacy, Sunrise University, Alwar (Raj.)

Abstract:

*Green chemistry emphasizes the need for environmentally hygienic synthesis, which informed improvement in selectivity, high atom efficiency, elimination of hazardous reagents, and easy separation with recovery and reuse of reagents. As a result, volatile organic solvents are being replaced by non-toxic, nonvolatile media such as ionic liquids, polyethylene glycol, and water. Alternatively, the reactions are carried out under solvent-free conditions. The phenomenal response, as evident from the growing number of publications, in order to achieve this goal is overwhelming. It is more advantageous to carry out reactions under solvent-free conditions. Particularly, in recent years, reactions under solvent-free conditions have continuously attracted the attention of researchers both from academia and industry. This is due to the fact that without solvent, reactions usually need shorter reaction time, simpler reactors, and require simple and efficient workup procedures. Spiro Indole thiazolidinones subsidiaries were set up by one pot buildup response of Isatin, thioglycolic corrosive and various amines utilizing a reactant measure of **p-TSA (p-toluenesulfonic acid)** is a modest and accessible impetus in EtOH under ultra sound light. The ideology is easy, starts from eagerly accessible commercial reactant materials, and provides biologically upgraded products in good yield and short reaction time. Spiro-indole-thiazolidinones derivatives are interesting heterocyclic compounds because they show diverse biological and pharmacological properties. Spiro-indole-thiazolidinones is examined as a life living important active scaffold that possesses almost whole type of microbial spotting.*

Key Words: p-TSA, Spiro Indole thiazolidinones, one pot synthesis, scaffold, sonicated.

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 22 July 2024

Accepted: 29 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

346

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13336451](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13336451)

Introduction

Thiazolidinone is a saturated form of thiazole with carbonyl group on 4th C and has been considered as a magic moiety which possesses almost all types of microscopic activities. In thiazolidinone ring, substitutions can occur on 2, 3 and 5 positions but substitution on 2nd position C atom ring exerts an admired effect on structure and property of thiazolidinones.

Thiazolidinone, a distinction privileged scaffold, is a very attractive target for combinatorial library synthesis because of their structure activity relationship and is an important class of N and S containing heterocycles, which are widely used as key building blocks in the field of drugs and pharmaceutical agents. Further, the presence of the N–C–S linkage in the thiazolidinone is also responsible for nematocidal, fungicidal, antibacterial and antiviral activities in addition, the spiro [indole-thiazolidine] system.

Thiazolidinone scaffold known to be associated with several biological activities such as anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-tubercular, anti-convulsant, anti-thyroid and antihistaminic activities.

Spiro –Thiazolidinones

The spiro compound is a bicyclic organic compound with rings connected through merely one point. The rings can be different in nature or photocopy. All the spiro compounds have infix spiro followed by square brackets containing number of atoms in the smaller rings and number of atoms in the larger ring excluding the spiro atom itself, the number being separated by a dot. Spiro-heterocyclics containing thiazolidine moiety has been recently shown to exhibit a wide array of interesting biological activities.

Objective of the Study:

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 22 July 2024

Accepted: 29 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

347

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13336451](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13336451)

One of the main objectives of the organic and medicinal chemistry instruction has been the design, synthesis and development of molecules having value as therapeutic agents. There are oodles of biologically active molecules with 5- membered rings containing 02 hetero atoms. Out of these thiazolidinone is an important scaffold known to be associated with several biological activities. It belongs to an important class of heterocyclic compounds containing S and N in a 05 member ring. Traditionally, thiazolidine, thiazolidinone and their spiro derivatives have been of great interest as sources of innovative drug candidates, with antimicrobial and antiviral effects.

Thiazolidinones represented a prestigious class of heterocyclic motifs that are found as a core structure component in a variety of medicinally active agents. 4- Thiazolidinones are compliments of thiazolidine with R-CO-R' group at the 4 position. Substitutions are possible at 2, 3 and 5 position respectively. The synthesis of thiazolidinone and their derivatives form major focus in medicinal chemistry on account of their armed accessibility, diverse chemical activity and profound multifarious biological medicinal properties e.g. analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, tuberculostatic, and hormone receptor, CNS stimulant, antiproliferative, anti-HIV and anticonvulsant, antihistaminic etc.

Spiro compounds are conspicuous to possess various pharmacological activities (and hence there has been synthesis a challenge and attraction to organic scholar). They have possessed very 'promising biological activities as anticancer, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, anti-tuberculosis, anti-Alzheimer, pain-relief, antidermatitis and antimicrobial agents. In addition to their medicinal uses, some spiro derivatives have found other uses in the agriculture, industrial field and they are also used as antifungal, pesticidal, laser dyes and electroluminescent devices'. Recently spiro derivatives have used as antioxidants. We were prompted by these findings to try to synthesize new spiro-thiazolidinone derivatives with potential anticonvulsant and antimicrobial properties.

Experiment

Herbal synthetic aspects of Spiro-Thiazolidinones

5,6-Dibromo-L-hypaphorine has been isolated from the South Pacific marine sponge *Hyrtios sp.* and displays weak inhibitory effects against bee venom phospholipase A2 (IC₅₀-inhibitory concentration to effect a 50% inhibition-0.2 mM) and a significant antioxidant activity.

Purpurines were isolated from the marine sponge *Iotrochota purpurea*, purpurine J (6-bromohypaphorine methylate, being the only indole-derived congener. Iodinated plakohypaphorines have been isolated from the Caribbean sponge *Plakortis simplex*. Diiodinated species plakohypaphorines exhibited significant “antihistaminic activity”. Examination of the organic extract of the broth of an unidentified algicolous fungus collected from the surface of the marine red alga *Gracilaria verrucosa* led to the isolation of Nb-acetyltryptamine. Analysis of the Red Sea marine sponge *Hyrtios erectus* led to the isolation of 5-hydroxy-1*H*-indole-3-carboxylic acid methyl ester, indole-3-carbaldehyde and 5-deoxyhyrtiosine A. Bacillamide A was obtained from the marine bacterium *Bacillus sp.* SY-1 and displayed algicidal activity against *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*. Bacillamides were found in a *Bacillus endophyticus*.

6-Hydroxydiscodermindole was obtained from the deep-water sponge *Discodermia polydiscus* and showed weak cytotoxic effects towards the murine leukemia cell line. 2-Methylsulfinyl-3-methylthio-4,5,6-tribromoindole, 3-methylsulfinyl-2,4,6-tribromo indole and 4,6-dibromo-2,3-di(methylsulfinyl)indole were isolated from the Formosan red alga *Laurencia brongniartii*. 2,3,4,6-Tetrabromo-1-methyl-1*H*-indole was isolated from the marine red alga *Laurencia decumbens*. 3,5,6-Tribromo-1*H*-indole, 3,5,6-tribromo-1-methyl-1*H*-indole, 2,3,6-tribromo-1*H*-indole, 3,5-dibromo-1-methyl-1*H*-indole and 2,5-dibromo-1-methyl-1*H*-indole have been isolated from the marine red alga *Laurencia similis*. 6-Bromo-1*H*-indole-3-carboxamide was obtained from the marine sponge *Mycale fibrexilis*. Dysinosins was isolated from the Australian sponge *Lamellodysidea chlorea*, while dysinosin A was obtained from an

Australian sponge of the family Dysideidae. Dysinosins exhibit inhibitory activity and thrombin with desulfated dysinosin being ten times less active. Granulatamides were isolated from the soft coral *Eunicella granulate* and showed cytotoxic activity against the tumor cell lines'. Functionalized heterocycles are interesting scaffold for the preparation of diversity oriented compound libraries for medicinal and pharmaceutical applications.

Conventional Method:

In a pilot experiment, a mixture of Isatin, amine and thioglycolic acid in the presence of a catalytic amount of *p*-TSA was sonicated at 50°C for 1.5 hrs. After completion of the reaction the crude product was separated from the reaction mixture by filtration and washed with C₂H₅-O-C₂H₅(10 ml) to afford product in higher weight.

To search for the optimal reaction solvent, this reaction was examined in H₂O, CH₂Cl₂ and EtOH at 50°C under ultrasonic irradiation. The reaction using ethanol as solvent result in higher ppt and little reaction time. To study the effect amount of the catalyst, the reaction was carried out at different amount of *p*-TSA ranging from 10-30 mol%.

In open capillaries M.P. can be taken. By TLC method we can evaluate the purity of compounds on precoated silica gel aluminum plates & visualized by exposure to ultraviolet light (254 nm) or iodine vapors. ¹H-NMR spectra of selected compound were recorded on multinuclear.

Fig. 1: Scheme for the synthesis of Spiro-indole-thiazolidinones derivatives

Table-1: Comparative study of products (in term of their yield & M.P.) obtained by changing the R-group in Aniline

Entry	Aniline	Product	Reaction time	Yield	M.P. (°C)
4a		1.5 h	85%	157	
4b		1.5 h	85%	192-194	
4c		1.5 h	83%	165-170	
4d		1.5 h	83%	125	
4e		1.5 h	87%	176-180	
4f		1.5 h	84%	182-184	

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 22 July 2024

Accepted: 29 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

351

 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13336451>

Table-2: Optimization of conditions

Entry	Conditions	<i>p</i> -TSA (mol%)	Time (hrs)	Yield%
1	EtOH/ 50°C/UV	None	5	<30
2	EtOH/ 50°C/UV	10	3	74
3	EtOH/ 50°C/UV	20	1.5	85
4	EtOH/ 50°C/UV	30	1.5	84
5	EtOH/ 40°C/UV	20	1.5	76
6	H ₂ O / 50°C/UV	20	5	<30
7	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /50°C/UV	20	5	45
8	CH ₃ CN/50°C/UV	20	5	55

Table-3: Difference b/w ultrasound irradiated yield and conventional heating yield

Entry	R	Ultrasound time(hrs)/ yield%	Conventional heating yield (%)
1	H	1.5/85	<30
2	Cl	2/83	<30
3	Br	2/84	<30
4	Me	1.5/84	<30
5	NO ₂	2/76	Trace

Result and Discussion

A mixture of (1) Isatin (1mol), (2) amine (1mol), (3) thioglycolic acid (1mol) and *p*-TSA (20 mol %) in EtOH (5 ml) was sonicated at 50°C for 1.5 hrs. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was filtered and the precipitate washed with diethyl ether to afford the neat product. To study the effect amount of the catalyst, the reaction was carried out at different amount of *p*-TSA ranging from 10-30 mol%. It was found that when increasing the amount of the *p*-TSA from 10-20 and 30 mol%, the yield increased. It was found that 20 mol% *p*-TSA in

ROH is sufficient to push this reaction forward. More amount of the additive did not improve the yields.

When the reaction was carried out without *p*-TSA the percentage of the expected product was very low. To optimize, the reaction temperature, we also performed several experiments at 25°C, 35°C, 40°C, and 50°C under ultrasonic irradiation. It was found that the use of ultrasound irradiation leads to a higher yield in shorter reaction time. On the other hand, when comparing the result obtained using conventional heating with ultrasound-assisted method, we can conclude that the main advantage of ultrasound is the significant decrease of reaction time and improvement of yields.

REFERENCES:

1. Puri, S., Kaur, B., Parmar, A., & Kumar, H. (2013). Applications of ultrasound in organic synthesis-A green approach. *Current Organic Chemistry*, 17, 1790-1828.
2. Ganem, B. (2009). Strategies for innovation in multicomponent reaction design. *Accounts of Chemical Research*, 42, 463-472.
3. Sundberg, R. (2016). *The Chemistry of Indoles: Part-I*. New York, NY : Academic press.
4. Ahadi, S. , Yasaei, Z., & Bazgir, A. (2019). A clean and one-pot synthesis of spiroindoline-pyranopyrazoles. *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 47, 1090-1094.
5. Gududuru, V., Hurh, E., Dalton, J. T., & Miller, D. D. (2014). Synthesis and antiproliferative activity of 2-aryl-4-oxo-thiazolidin-3-yl-amides for prostate cancer. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 14, 5289-5293.
6. Ottan, R., Carotti, S., Maccari, R., Landini, I., Chiricosta, G., Caciagli, B., Vigorita, M. G., & Mini, E. (2015). In vitro antiproliferative activity against human colon cancer cell lines of representative 4-thiazolidinones. part-1. *Bioorganic Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 15, 3930-3933

7. Singh, G. S., & Desta, Z. Y. (2012). Isatins as privileged molecules in design and synthesis of spiro fused cyclic frameworks. *Chemical Reviews*, *112*, 6104-6155.
8. Pahari, N., Saha, D., Jain, V. K., Jain, B., & Mridha, D. (2010). Synthesis and evaluation of acute toxicity studies and analgesic characters of some novel indole derivatives. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research*, *1*, 399-408.
9. Lesyk, R., Zimenkovsky, B., Atamanyuk, D., Jenson, F., Kiec-Kononowicz, K., & Gzella, A. (2016). Anticancer thiopyrano[2,3-d][1,3]thiazol-2-ones with norbornane moiety. synthesis, cytotoxicity, physico-chemical properties, and computational studies. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*, *14*, 5230-5240.
10. Prabhakar, Y. S., Solomon, V. R., Gupta, M. K., & Katti, S. B. (2016). QSAR and molecular modeling studies in heterocyclic drugs II. *Top. Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, *4*, 161-249.
11. Pandeya, S.N., Smitha, S., Jyoti, M., & Sridhar, S. K. (2015). Biological activities of isatin and its derivatives. *Acta Pharmaceutica*, *55*, 27-46.